

TYCHO Astrometry - Mathematical Formulation

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report is mainly a collection of definitions and mathematical relations, forming a theoretical basis for deriving astrometric results from the TYCHO data. Definitions are closely linked to those used by NDAC in the processing of the main HIPPARCOS mission. Their exact relationship with FAST concepts will have to be established at a later point.

2. PURPOSE OF THE ASTROMETRY TASK (WP6000)

The purpose is to determine the five astrometric parameters (position and proper motion components and the parallax) for each TYCHO star, for which a sufficient number of observations ('identified transits') have been collected. The task combines mainly the following three kinds of information:

- (i) *transit times*, i.e. the observed instants at which the star crosses certain fiducial lines on the focal surface of the telescope; these are the output of a previous step of the TYCHO data analysis --
- (ii) *attitude data*, describing the celestial pointing (coordinates of the viewing directions) as function of time; these are determined as part of the main mission processing and will be supplied by FAST and/or NDAC --
- (iii) *grid calibration data*, which describe the geometry of the fiducial lines with respect to the viewing directions. These are in turn assembled from laboratory measurements of the grid, in-orbit calibrations during commissioning and as part of the main processing, and from corrections derived in the course of the astrometry task itself.

Broadly speaking, each identified transit defines a position line for the star on the sky, namely, the projection onto the celestial sphere of the fiducial line at the time of transit. This projection can be calculated by means of (ii) and (iii). The intersection of several such position lines provides the astrometric position of the star, and its variation with time gives the proper motion and parallax. In practice, a least-squares solution is made of the astrometric parameters, using linearized coordinates within a small area around the expected position (from the TIC).

3. BASIC CONCEPTS AND DEFINITIONS

3.1. Celestial Coordinate System

It is very strongly recommended that all calculations on celestial directions are made in a single, well-defined coordinate system being as close as possible to the final system in which the Catalogue will be published. This is the mean equatorial system at the standard epoch J2000.0. Since the observations are completely decoupled from the rotation of the Earth, there is no sense in using any other epoch, and precession and nutation will not appear in any calculation.

The equatorial system J2000.0 is conceptually defined by two inertial and orthogonal directions: towards the North Celestial Pole ($\delta = 90^\circ$), as represented by the unit vector $\mathbf{n}$, and towards the vernal equinox ($\alpha = \delta = 0^\circ$, unit vector $\mathbf{l}$). Defining a third unit vector $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{l}$ ($\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\delta = 0^\circ$), we may represent the system most compactly by means of the vector triad $\mathbf{N} = [\mathbf{l} \ \mathbf{m} \ \mathbf{n}]$. The components of any vector $\mathbf{r}$ in this system, i.e. its rectangular equatorial coordinates, are given by the three scalars $l = \mathbf{l}'\mathbf{r}$, $m = \mathbf{m}'\mathbf{r}$, $n = \mathbf{n}'\mathbf{r}$ (with ' denoting scalar product) or by the 3×1 matrix

$$\mathbf{N}'\mathbf{r} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{l}' \\ \mathbf{m}' \\ \mathbf{n}' \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{r} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{l}'\mathbf{r} \\ \mathbf{m}'\mathbf{r} \\ \mathbf{n}'\mathbf{r} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} l \\ m \\ n \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

It is important to notice the distinction between the vector ($\mathbf{r}$) and its components with respect to some vector triad (such as $\mathbf{N}'\mathbf{r}$); the former is purely a direction in space (with a certain length), while the latter is a column matrix. Naturally, all numerical computation is made on scalars (matrix elements) and not vectors: any vector equation like $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{c}$ must be translated to a matrix equation like $\mathbf{N}'\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{N}'\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{N}'\mathbf{c}$ (if $\mathbf{N}$ happens to

be a convenient coordinate frame) before it can be dealt with by the computer.

3.2. Time

The time scale used throughout this note is denoted T and is reckoned in SI seconds (TDT) from the instant J1988.0 TDT = 1988 January 1, 12^h TDT. This is exactly 0.12 Julian centuries before the standard epoch J2000.0 and thus a suitable origin to avoid negative or excessively large numbers. For our purposes it is not necessary to distinguish between terrestrial dynamical time (TDT) and barycentric dynamical time (TDB).

3.3. Ephemerides

For the calculation of parallax, gravitational light deflection, and aberration, we can assume that accurate ephemerides are available for the sun (S) and observer (O). They are expressed as rectangular equatorial coordinates of S and O with respect to the Solar System Barycentre and as functions of time: $N'b_S(T)$ and $N'b_O(T)$, where b_S , b_O are the barycentric vectors. The unit is [m].

3.4. Telescope Coordinate System

The optical system of HIPPARCOS provides two *viewing directions* f_1 and f_{-1} (unit vectors), being the celestial projections of the centre of the main grid. The telescope system is represented by the vector triad $Z = [x \ y \ z]$, where $x = \langle f_{-1} + f_1 \rangle$ is the bisector and $z = \langle f_{-1} \times f_1 \rangle$ the normal of the viewing directions, and $y = z \times x$. ($\langle \rangle$ denotes vector normalization, $\langle r \rangle = r/|r|$ for any vector of length $|r| > 0$.) See Fig. 1.

The (acute) angle between f_{-1} and f_1 is known as the *basic angle* (γ), close to 58° . The viewing directions can then be expressed as

$$f_f = x \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma + y f \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma, \quad f = -1, 1 \quad (2)$$

It is convenient to regard γ as a numerical constant (to be fixed once and for all presumably after in-orbit commissioning), rather than a changing instrumental parameter. Then f_{-1} and f_1 do not represent strictly

the same point on the grid, but this difference is quite naturally absorbed in the geometrical description of the grid (Section 3.7).

3.5. Attitude

The attitude, or celestial orientation of the telescope system, is most generally represented by the (orthogonal) 3×3 matrix

$$A(T) = N'Z = \begin{bmatrix} l'x & l'y & l'z \\ m'x & m'y & m'z \\ n'x & n'y & n'z \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

in which the elements are continuous functions of time. This is not a very compact representation, however, because of the redundancy of the matrix elements (the orthogonality implies six constraints among them), and it is customary to write the attitude matrix as the product of three or more elementary rotation matrices; the rotation angles then provide a non-redundant attitude representation. The decomposition used by NDAC is the following:

$$A = A_1(\varepsilon)A_3(\lambda_S)A_1(\nu - \frac{1}{2}\pi)A_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \xi)A_3(\Omega) \quad (4)$$

with $A_i(\phi)$, $i = 1, 2, 3$ denoting a rotation by the angle ϕ about the i 'th axis,

$$A_1(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c\phi & -s\phi \\ 0 & s\phi & c\phi \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_2(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta & 0 & s\theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s\theta & 0 & c\theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_3(\psi) = \begin{bmatrix} c\psi & -s\psi & 0 \\ s\psi & c\psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$\varepsilon = 23^{\circ}26'21''.448$ is the mean obliquity of the ecliptic and λ_S the longitude of the 'nominal sun' (given by an exact formula as function of T , approximating the true longitude of the sun to within an arcmin). The attitude is thus given by the three 'heliotropic' angles $\nu(T)$, $\xi(T)$, $\Omega(T)$. These have a simple interpretation in terms of the satellite's orientation with respect to the sun (Fig. 2).

An efficient FORTRAN subroutine for calculating A , given T , ν , ξ , and Ω , is available from NDAC/LO (subroutine ATTIT, TDAC-TD020).

3.6. Field Coordinates

Let $\mathbf{u}$ be the unit vector in the proper (apparent) direction of a star. The rectangular coordinates of $\mathbf{u}$ can be expressed in the equatorial system as

$$N'u = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \delta \cos \alpha \\ \cos \delta \sin \alpha \\ \sin \delta \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

and in the telescope system as

$$Z'u = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The two column matrices are related by the orthogonal transformation A (attitude matrix):

$$N'u = N'ZZ'u = AZ'u \quad (8)$$

since $ZZ' = U$ (the unit tensor). Equation (8) and the inverse relation $Z'u = A'N'u$ (since $A^{-1} = A'$) are the numerical expressions used for transforming between the two system.

The case of interest is when $\mathbf{u}$ is close to either $\mathbf{f}_{-1}$ or $\mathbf{f}_1$, i.e. when the star is within either field of view. A coordinate representation slightly more convenient than (7) is then obtained with respect to the vector triad oriented along the viewing direction,

$$ZA_3(\frac{1}{2}f\gamma) = [f_f \quad z \times f_f \quad z] \quad (9)$$

with $f = \pm 1$ depending on which field the star is in. The coordinate components of $\mathbf{u}$ are then

$$[ZA_3(\frac{1}{2}f\gamma)]'u = A_3'(\frac{1}{2}f\gamma)Z'u = \begin{bmatrix} x \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma + y f \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma \\ y \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma - x f \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma \\ z \end{bmatrix} =: \begin{bmatrix} (1-w^2-z^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ w \\ z \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

and (w, z) are called the *field coordinates* of the object. The *field index* (f) is in practice given by the sign of y .

3.7. Starmapper geometry

The starmapper grid consists of several slits arranged in two groups, the 'vertical' group ($g = 1$) and the 'chevron' group ($g = 2$). See Figure 3. For the present task we are not concerned with individual slits, however, but only with the centre line or *fiducial line* of each group. This line can be thought of as the centre of gravity of the four slits in a group, taken along the scanning (or w) direction. The fiducial lines are defined, in field coordinates, by means of the equations

$$w - w_{fg}^*(z) = 0 \quad (f = \pm 1, g = 1, 2) \quad (11)$$

The derivation of the functions $w_{fg}^*(z)$ from grid calibration data (laboratory measurements, great-circle reductions, etc) is discussed in the note NDAC/LO/063.[†] As for the analytical form of these functions, the following representation is probably adequate:

$$w_{f1}^*(z) = fh + w_{10} + w_{11}z + w_{12}z^2 \quad (\text{vertical}) \quad (12a)$$

$$w_{f2}^*(z) = fh + w_{20} + \begin{cases} w_{21}^+z + w_{22}^+z^2, & z > 0 \\ w_{21}^-z + w_{22}^-z^2, & z < 0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{chevron}) \quad (12b)$$

Nominally, the starmapper slits are straight lines in the (w, z) plane and we have $h, w_{11}, w_{12}, w_{22}^+, w_{22}^- \simeq 0$, $w_{21}^+ \simeq -1$, and $w_{21}^- \simeq 1$; $w_{10} \simeq 0.00938$ and $w_{20} \simeq 0.01545$. (All signs are reversed for the starmapper grid on the $-w$ side of the main grid.) The parameter h accounts for any deviation of the actual basic angle from the adopted constant value γ (Section 3.4). Note that the two branches of the chevron fiducial line meet exactly at $z = 0$, which is in fact the definition of origin of that coordinate.

Let (w, z) be the field coordinates and f the field index of an object at a certain instant. Its 'distance' from slit group g can be defined as

$$u_g = w - w_{fg}^*(z) \quad (13)$$

and the transit time τ is the instant at which $u_g = 0$. The observations consist of measured transit times τ_{obs} associated with a specific object.

[†] The results of that study refer to the geometry of the principal ray and will require some revision to take into account the actual beam of each half-pupil.

4. DETERMINATION OF ASTROMETRIC PARAMETERS

The five astrometric parameters for star i are: α_i , δ_i , Π_i , $\mu_{\alpha i}$, $\mu_{\delta i}$. (Π = trigonometric parallax) In principle, they are determined by a least-squares fit to the observed transit times of the star, τ_{obs} , of which some 200 will be obtained for an average star. The solution is closely linked to the determination of (improved) grid parameters h , w_{10} , ..., and the formulation below takes full account of this calibration, even if it may not be fully utilized.

4.1. Observation Equation

For each observed transit (τ_{obs}) of star i on slit group g , the following observation equation can be set up:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \alpha_i} \Delta \alpha_i + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \delta_i} \Delta \delta_i + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \Pi_i} \Delta \Pi_i + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \mu_{\alpha i}} \Delta \mu_{\alpha i} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial \mu_{\delta i}} \Delta \mu_{\delta i} + \\ + \frac{\partial u}{\partial h} \Delta h + \frac{\partial u}{\partial w_{10}} \Delta w_{10} + \dots + \frac{\partial u}{\partial w_{22}^-} \Delta w_{22}^- + \text{noise} = u_{\text{obs}} - u_{\text{calc}} \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

Here, $u_{\text{obs}} = 0$ is the observed distance of the star from the fiducial line at time τ_{obs} , and u_{calc} the distance calculated from current values of the astrometric parameters (normally just the TIC position), grid calibration parameters, and the attitude. $\Delta \alpha_i$, ..., Δw_{22}^- are the corrections to these current parameters, to be determined by the least-squares method. Expressions for calculating u_{calc} , the partial derivatives in (14), and the weight of the observation (or, rather, the estimated variance of the noise term) are given in the next three sections.

4.2. Calculation of u_{calc} in (14)

Calculation of u_{calc} from field coordinates (f , w , z) was described in Section 3.7, while the transformations from proper direction to field coordinates were given in Section 3.6. It remains to specify the calculation of $\mathbf{N}'u_i$, the proper direction at time $T = \tau_{\text{obs}}$ in equatorial coordinates. This is done from the astrometric parameters and ephemerides by the following steps.

(A) Introduce the two column matrices

$$N'd_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \delta_i \cos \alpha_i \\ \cos \delta_i \sin \alpha_i \\ \sin \delta_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$N'\mu_i = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu_{\alpha i} \cos \delta_i \sin \alpha_i & -\mu_{\delta i} \sin \delta_i \cos \alpha_i \\ \mu_{\alpha i} \cos \delta_i \cos \alpha_i & -\mu_{\delta i} \sin \delta_i \sin \alpha_i \\ & \mu_{\delta i} \cos \delta_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

The coordinate direction of the star at time T is then, in equatorial coordinates,

$$N'\bar{u}_i = \langle N'd_i + N'\mu_i(T - T_0) - N'b_0(T)/A \rangle \quad (17)$$

if T_0 is the proper motion epoch (preferably close to mid-mission) and A the astronomical unit. $\langle \rangle$ signifies division by the Euclidean norm of the column matrix (corresponding to vector normalization).

(B) Application of gravitational light deflection by the sun, according to General Relativity, gives the coordinates of the natural direction:

$$N'\hat{u}_i = \langle N'\bar{u}_i + N'h_0\omega \rangle, \quad (18a)$$

$$\omega = 2GSe^{-2} [|h_0| (|h_0| + \bar{u}_i^T h_0)]^{-1} \quad (18b)$$

$h_0 = b_0 - b_s$ is the heliocentric position of the observer and $2GSe^{-2} = 2953.25$ m the Schwarzschild radius of the sun.

(C) The proper direction is finally obtained by a Lorentz transformation to the co-moving frame:

$$N'u_i = \langle N'\hat{u}_i + N'v_0 [1 + v_0^T \hat{u}_i (c + e)^{-1}] e^{-1} \rangle, \quad (19a)$$

$$e = (c^2 - v_0^T v_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (19b)$$

where $v_0 = db_0/dT$ is the barycentric velocity of the satellite and c the velocity of light.

4.3. Calculation of partial derivatives in (14)

Let

$$t_g(z) = \frac{dw_g^*}{dz} \approx \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } g = 1 \\ \pm 1 & \text{for } g = 2 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

and introduce the vector

$$\mathbf{p} = y \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma - x f \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma - z t_g(z) \quad (21)$$

so that, approximately, $u_g = \mathbf{p}' \mathbf{u}_i - w_{fg}^*(0)$. Hence (neglecting gravitational deflection and aberration in this calculation)

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \alpha_i} = \mathbf{p}' \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial \alpha_i} = \mathbf{p}' (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u}_i) \quad (22a)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \delta_i} = \mathbf{p}' \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial \delta_i} = \mathbf{p}' (\mathbf{u}_i \times \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u}_i \rangle) \quad (22b)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \Pi_i} = \mathbf{p}' \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial \Pi_i} = -\mathbf{p}' b_0(T)/A \quad (22c)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial \mu \alpha_i} = (T - T_0) \frac{\partial u}{\partial \alpha_i}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial \mu \delta_i} = (T - T_0) \frac{\partial u}{\partial \delta_i} \quad (22d,e)$$

For the practical computation it can be noted that

$$\mathbf{N}' \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{N}' \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{Z}' \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{A} \begin{bmatrix} -f \sin \frac{1}{2}\gamma \\ \cos \frac{1}{2}\gamma \\ -t_g(z) \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

from (3) and (21), while the matrices

$$\mathbf{N}' (\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u}_i) = \begin{bmatrix} -\cos \delta_i \sin \alpha_i \\ \cos \delta_i \cos \alpha_i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{N}' (\mathbf{u}_i \times \langle \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{u}_i \rangle) = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin \delta_i \cos \alpha_i \\ -\sin \delta_i \sin \alpha_i \\ \cos \delta_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

are the same that appear in (16).

The partial derivatives with respect to the grid geometry parameters $h, w_{10}, \dots, w_{22}$ are immediately obtained from (12)-(13); they are all 0, -1, -z, or $-z^2$.

4.4. Calculation of expected rms noise in (14)

The uncertainty of the right-hand side of (14) depends on two error sources: photon-statistical uncertainty of the observed transit time (σ_τ), and attitude uncertainty. If $\mathbf{C}$ is the 3×3 covariance matrix of the attitude angles (ν, ξ, Ω), we have formally

$$\sigma_u^2 = |\dot{u}|^2 \sigma_\tau^2 + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial \Omega} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{C} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \nu} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial \Omega} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (25)$$

with $\dot{u} = du/dT \simeq 8.18 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ rad s}^{-1}$. Considering the way in which the attitude is determined, it is not unreasonable to assume, for the present purpose, that the attitude errors in calculated (w, z) are uncorrelated and characterized by nearly constant standard deviations σ_w, σ_z . Then, using that $|t_2| \simeq 1$, we have to sufficient accuracy

$$\sigma_u^2 = |\dot{u}|^2 \sigma_\tau^2 + \sigma_w^2 + \delta_{g2} \sigma_z^2 \quad (26)$$

where $\delta_{g2} = 0$ for the vertical group and 1 for the chevron group.

The photonstatistical error σ_τ is calculated for each transit as function of the estimated star and background count rates, while $\dot{u}, \sigma_w$, and σ_u are thus regarded as given constants.

4.5. Least-squares solution

Dividing Eq. (14) by the estimated standard deviation σ_u from Eq. (26) gives an observation equation of unit weight. We shall assume that the grid calibration requires, for the whole mission, a total of N_c parameters [e.g. $N_c = 9$ if the form (12) applies], and that there are a total of I stars ($i = 1, 2, \dots, I$) and K observations ($k = 1, 2, \dots, K$).

The k th observation equation can be written in matrix form

$$\mathbf{B}_k \Delta \mathbf{a}_{i(k)} + \mathbf{C}_k \Delta \mathbf{c} + v_k = e_k \quad (27)$$

with $i(k)$ denoting the star associated with observation k and

$$\mathbf{B}_k = \left[\begin{array}{cccc} \frac{1}{\sigma_u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \alpha_{i(k)}} & \frac{1}{\sigma_u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \delta_{i(k)}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sigma_u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \mu_{\delta i(k)}} \end{array} \right]_k \quad (1 \times 5) \quad (28a)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_k = \left[\begin{array}{cccc} \frac{1}{\sigma_u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial h} & \frac{1}{\sigma_u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \omega_{10}} & \cdots & \frac{1}{\sigma_u} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \omega_{22}^-} \end{array} \right]_k \quad (1 \times N_c) \quad (28b)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{a}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \alpha_i \\ \Delta \delta_i \\ \Delta \Pi_i \\ \Delta \mu_{\alpha i} \\ \Delta \mu_{\delta i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5 \times 1) \quad (28c)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{c} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta h \\ \Delta \omega_{10} \\ \vdots \\ \Delta \omega_{22}^- \end{bmatrix} \quad (N_c \times 1) \quad (28d)$$

$$e_k = (u_{\text{obs}} - u_{\text{calc}}) / \sigma_u \quad (28e)$$

v_k is a centred random variable with unit variance, $E(v_k) = 0$, $E(v_k^2) = 1$.

Introducing the matrices

$$\mathbf{D}_i = \sum_{k \in i} \mathbf{B}_k' \mathbf{B}_k \quad (5 \times 5) \quad (29a)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_i = \sum_{k \in i} \mathbf{B}_k' \mathbf{C}_k \quad (5 \times N_c) \quad (29b)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_i = \sum_{k \in i} \mathbf{B}_k' e_k \quad (5 \times 1) \quad (29c)$$

$$\mathbf{G} = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{C}_k' \mathbf{C}_k \quad (N_c \times N_c) \quad (29d)$$

$$\mathbf{h} = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{C}_k' e_k \quad (N_c \times 1) \quad (29e)$$

the normal equations become

$$D_i \Delta a_i + E_i \Delta c = f_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, I \quad (30a)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^I E_i^T D_i^{-1} \Delta a_i + G \Delta c = h \quad (30b)$$

Elimination of each Δa_i yields the following equation for the calibration parameters:

$$\left[G - \sum_{i=1}^I E_i^T D_i^{-1} E_i \right] \Delta c = h - \sum_{i=1}^I E_i^T D_i^{-1} f_i \quad (31)$$

With

$$\Delta a_i^{(0)} = D_i^{-1} f_i \quad (32)$$

denoting the astrometric solution obtained by *neglecting* the corrections to the calibration parameters [by putting $\Delta c = 0$ in (30a)] we then have by back-substitution the following *rigorous* astrometric solution:

$$\Delta a_i = \Delta a_i^{(0)} - D_i^{-1} E_i \Delta c \quad (33)$$

The $(5 \times N_c)$ matrix $D_i^{-1} E_i$ thus summarizes the *sensitivity* of the astrometric parameters to grid calibration errors, and can be used for posterior correction of the former, once an improved calibration has been derived [by means of (31) or any other method]. Provided that N_c is not too large, it will be advantageous to store this 'sensitivity matrix' along with the preliminary solution, rather than re-computing the observation and normal equations with the improved grid calibration.

FIGURE 1. Definition of the telescope axes X , Y , Z in terms of the viewing directions f_{-1} and f_1 .

FIGURE 2. The celestial orientation of the telescope axes (the attitude) is given with respect to the equatorial system by means of the angles ϵ , λ_s , ν , ξ , and Ω .

FIGURE 3. Field coordinates (w , z) and starmapper geometry.